

Title: Making Your Big Data Plans Work

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INTRODUCTION:

To be a market leader your company must change, adapt, and outpace its competition. One financially feasible way of doing this is by turning your company into a data-driven organization using Big Data. However, to succeed in doing this, your company must build new competencies in its leadership, management, and talent. Many companies are just not ready to take advantage of all that Big Data has to offer.

AIM:

To provide guidelines for the conversations, human resources, and training needed for building effective data-driven organizations using Big Data, leadership, change management, projects, programs, and technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Three companies and their approaches towards building data-driven organizations are examined and compared. Comparisons are made between each company's desired business outcomes, definitions, team structures, skill sets, planning, training, designing, and execution.

RESULTS:

Each company failed at their first attempt of building data-driven organizations. The reasons for these high failure rates are "solutioning" over designing, narrowed scoping, leadership personalities, and using transactional approaches to address transformational needs.

CONCLUSIONS:

To reduce the high level of failure for building data-driven organizations, your company must develop clear guidelines first before making any significant investments in Big Data.

KEYWORDS:

Big Data, Plan, Project, Program, Data-Driven, Leadership

BIOGRAPHY:

Chris Pehura is a practice director for C-SUITE DATA; a boutique consulting firm that helps clients expand their competencies in leadership, change management, and data-driven organizations. He's led end-to-end transformational initiatives for Fortune clients. Initiatives included shifting culture, smoothing M&A, reinventing core processes, launching new products, and leveraging massive amounts of data. He has also designed post-graduate academic programs

geared for expanding competencies in leadership, management, and data. He holds a computer engineering degree from the University of Manitoba, Canada and has a passion for how artificial intelligence makes people better people.